
MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM – LYMPHATIC PROTOCOL PRESENTATION

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Maria Helena Carreiro Barros de Almeida¹

Mildes Mendes Pereira¹

Rebeca Bastos dos Santos Gonçalves¹

Adriane Viapiana Bossa²

Angela Mara Rambo Martini³

ABSTRACT

Integrative and Complementary Techniques in healthcare can improve quality of life in when used alone or in conjunction with other therapies. The Lymphatic System (LS) is a pathway of the circulatory system that allows fluids from interstitial spaces to flow into the blood as lymph through a network of lymphatic vessels. Dysfunctional activity of the LS can lead to conditions such as lymphedema, metastasis, and is also associated with various inflammatory disorders. Inadequate lymphatic drainage occurs due to obstruction within the LS, particularly in the lymph nodes. In this context, Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is used to improve lymphatic drainage processes. MB is a technique with therapeutic potential in promoting, preventing, and treating health conditions, utilizing static magnetic fields (SMF) from therapeutic magnets. This study has the aim to present the lymphatic protocol (LP) of MB. This work consists of an

exploratory, descriptive, literature review with a qualitative approach on the use of the LP. The literature base includes articles, books, handouts, and theses. After the selection and review of the literature, it was possible to give support the proposed application of the lymphatic protocol in the MB technique. In this regard, the LP is presented. It should be studied to evaluate its effects on symptoms resulting from alterations in lymphatic flow.

Keywords: Medicinal Biomagnetism; Static Magnetic Fields; Lymphatic Protocol; Magnetotherapy; Lymphatic System; Lymphatic Drainage.

INTRODUCTION

The Lymphatic System (LS) is an accessory pathway of the circulatory system allowing fluids from the interstitial spaces to flow into the blood as lymph, through a network of lymphatic vessels, collecting ducts, and lymph nodes (OLGUIN et al., 2022).

Lymph is a substance composed of proteins and other macromolecules, cellular metabolic products, and pathogens that cannot be absorbed by the blood capillaries and accumulate in the tissue spaces. Lymph enters the lymph nodes through afferent lymphatic vessels and is slowly filtered. After filtration, lymph leaves the lymph nodes through efferent lymphatic vessels (OLGUIN et al., 2022).

In addition to its function of capturing excess fluid from the interstitial spaces and distributing it to the bloodstream, the LS is involved in other vital processes such as the destruction of microorganisms and foreign particles in the lymph, removal of cellular metabolites, surveillance of defense mechanisms, regulation of water balance, absorption and transport of macronutrients, and fluid return to the bloodstream (DA SILVA, 2020).

This return occurs through a network of channels, starting with lymphatic capillaries, then pre-collector vessels, collector vessels, lymph nodes, lymphatic trunks, and finally, lymphatic ducts. The impulse for this transport depends on passive contractility, such as respiratory movements, skeletal muscle

contractions, and smooth muscle movements of the lymphatic vessels (MARQUES; SILVA, 2020).

When the LS fails to filter and/or drain all the fluid that accumulates in the interstitium, it results in edema, which can be localized or generalized, and is closely related to inflammatory, infectious, and metastatic processes due to the dissemination of cancer cells throughout the body (MARQUES; SILVA, 2020; CUENI, 2008).

The accumulation of particles in the lymphatic vessels and lymph nodes leads to changes in these structures, triggering a local inflammatory and infectious response, which may present with increased volume, heat, pain, and the occurrence of lymphangitis, lymphadenitis, as well as secondary cancer (OLGUIN et al., 2022; DA SILVA, 2020).

According to Moore (2014), lymphangitis is a secondary inflammation of the lymphatic vessels, and lymphadenitis occurs in the lymph nodes. They can also be caused by chemicals, microorganisms, and after severe injury or infection. Lymphedema occurs when lymph cannot flow properly due to abnormalities in the LS, leading to its accumulation in the interstitial space and the formation of edema (OLGUIN et al., 2022).

Lymphedema can have congenital origins resulting from malformation of the lymphatic channels or lymph nodes, or it can be acquired throughout life in situations such as trauma, injuries, infectious diseases, lymph node removal surgery (lymphadenectomies), radiation therapy in the lymph node region, metastatic cancer, and others. It is a chronic, severe, and progressive condition, more common in the upper and lower limbs, but it can occur in any body area (OLGUIN et al., 2022).

Edema is a sign that may characterize an LS alteration, caused by a deficiency in the normal exchanges between the circulatory and lymphatic systems. Generally, edema occurs due to inadequate lymph drainage or excessive capillary blood filtration, exceeding the capacity of capillary absorption (SILVERTHORN, 2017).

To accelerate the absorption of mild edemas, the most commonly used procedures in conventional medicine are elevation of the affected area to facilitate edema and inflammatory substance drainage by gravity, maintaining hydrated skin to prevent dryness and new lesions, and regular physical exercises (VALIATI, 2012; CHAVES; GREGOLIS, 2018).

In more severe cases, ice packs, compression measures, elevation of the affected limb, manual lymphatic drainage (MLD), elastic containment measures, and pharmacological treatment when the infectious agent is known are recommended (VALIATI, 2012; TÁBOAS, 2013). MLD is a widely used procedure aimed at reducing edema and lymphedema, as well as preventing or improving their consequences (ALENCAR, 2011).

According to Táboas et al. (2013), the choice of lymphedema treatment requires an individual evaluation, considering the location, severity, stage of lymphedema, as well as associated comorbidities and psychological condition. The procedures used contribute to reducing edema; however, there is no evidence of efficacy in restoring proper lymphatic system functioning (TÁBOAS, 2013; CHAVES; GREGOLIS, 2018).

Due to the difficulty to find definitive treatments for pathologies related to the lymphatic system, traditional medicine has increasingly sought the integration of complementary treatments alongside conventional therapies. Such practices are defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as Traditional, Complementary, and Integrative Medicines (TCIM) (BRAZIL, 2018).

This term refers to a broad set of health care practices based on theories and experiences from different cultures, used for health promotion, prevention, and recovery, taking into consideration the holistic view of the individual and bringing significant benefits to conventional therapies (MENDES et al., 2019; BRAZIL, 2018).

Magnetotherapy is a therapeutic practice that uses Static Magnetic Fields (SMF) generated by magnets and aims to complement the treatment of certain health conditions, such as pain, injuries, and inflammations (DURÁN, 2008; RIBEIRO,

2016; MACEDO et al., 2023; FRANCO et al., 2023; RAVAGNANI FILHO et al., 2023; BARBOSA et al., 2023; BUENO et al., 2023; PELISSARI; BOSSA, 2023; DRUM et al., 2023; CORRÊA et al., 2023; SANTOS et al., 2023; MOREIRA et al., 2023). Magnets generate magnetic fields (MF) due to the rotation of electrons within the material itself (PITTLER, 2007; FOLTRAN et al., 2023; CALEGARI et al., 2023). To treat the organism with magnetic fields, considering its bioenergetic imbalance, factors such as cell rotation, pH, oxygen levels, the magnets used, the effects of magnetic poles, and the body's reaction to magnetic stimulation should be taken into account (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; RAMBO MARTINI et al., 2023; LIMA et al., 2023; CAZELLA et al., 2023; SANTOS, P. et al., 2023; SANTOS, L. et al., 2023; ARAÚJO; FERREIRA; BOSSA, 2023; FRANK, 2017; DAMYANOV et al., 2019a; DAMYANOV et al., 2019b).

According to Broeringmeyer (1991), a healthy cell rotates to the left, and its nucleus rotates to the right, generating energy. The opposite occurs in a diseased cell, which uses this energy to sustain the disease.

Hydrogen is essential to balance energy and promote cell normality. Thus, when any disease starts, there is an increase in hydrogen and a decrease in oxygen, causing hyperactivity and acidity in the affected area, leading to inflammation and, consequently, edema (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; FOLTRAN et al., 2023; BOSSA, C. et al., 2023). Durán (2008) argues that the energy of the north and south poles has the ability to move hydrogen and oxygen, which can be beneficial to bring the organism to a state of balance and stabilize the body's bioelectricity.

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) applies the concept of magnetotherapy to living beings, studying the relationship and interrelation of magnetic and electromagnetic phenomena generated by magnets in the organism (DURÁN, 2008; FOLTRAN et al., 2023; BOSSA, C. et al., 2023). It is a non-invasive therapeutic technique developed in 1988 by Isaac Goiz Durán, applying SMF of medium intensity – from 1000 to 7500 Gauss – on dysfunctional anatomical points that resonate with each other, called Biomagnetic Pairs (BMP) (DURÁN, 2005; DURÁN, 2008; FRANK, 2017).

After more than 30 years of daily clinical practice by Biomagnetism professionals, numerous protocols have been developed for various pathologies (BOSSA, 2021; MARTÍNEZ, 2017). Among these protocols (MACEDO et al., 2023; FRANCO et al., 2023; RAVAGNANI FILHO et al., 2023; BARBOSA et al., 2023; BUENO et al., 2023; PELISSARI; BOSSA, 2023; DRUM et al., 2023; CORRÊA et al., 2023; SANTOS et al., 2023; MOREIRA et al., 2023), Lymphatic Protocol (LP) is a result of the practice of Biomagnetist Adrian, a student of the Instituto Par Magnético (IPM), a Brazilian MB school that follows the original line of the technique developed by Isaac Goiz Durán.

In 2018, Adrian applied the north pole of MB magnets to the regions of the lymph nodes, as described by Calegari et al. (2023), with the intention of tonifying the thymus, which is part of the lymphatic system. He also applied the south pole of a therapeutic magnet over the gland and left the magnets impacted overnight. The next morning, Adrian's grandmother sent him a photo of her legs, which were already free of edema. The edema did not return (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Before and after of the LP application (BMP) developed and applied by Adrian.

The first image shows edematous lower limbs before receiving the LP; the subsequent images are from the day after the application and the following days. Source: Bossa (2021).

Based on this experience, this study aims to propose the application of the Lymphatic Protocol (PL) using MB magnets as a tool to drain and detoxify,

optimizing the lymphatic system's function.

METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive study of an exploratory nature, conducted through a literature review. According to Freitas (2017), the descriptive method is used to describe, differentiate, and examine existing associations, particularly when the topic is scarce. The narrative presents the found facts, and in both cases, the researcher acts as an observer. It is exploratory as it fills the gaps in a study, as conducted in this research.

The research was carried out on the online platforms SciELO, Google Scholar, PubMed, and the Library of the Instituto Par Magnético (IPM). Manual searches were also conducted through bibliographic references found in books, articles, and course materials related to Biomagnetic Therapy due to the scarcity of published content.

To select the articles, the title and abstract were first read. Then, the pre-selected articles were read in full to evaluate their compatibility with the inclusion criteria previously established for the study.

The used keywords were: lymphatic system; lymphatic drainage; lymphedema; medical biomagnetism; magnetotherapy; static magnetic fields; integrative practices.

As inclusion criteria, publications on the subject in the last 20 years in Portuguese, Spanish, and English were used, with a focus on articles related to the topic. Articles that did not cover the subject, duplicates, and those published before the selected year were excluded.

After selecting and reading the established literature, the researchers were able to synthesize the topic to support the proposal of the lymphatic protocol using the MB technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a result of the methodological search, 42 references were found, comprising nine on the Lymphatic System, six on Static Magnetic Fields (SMF), 24 on Medical Biomagnetism (MB), two on Integrative Practices (IP), and one on Scientific Methodology, all used to support this study. The references included articles, books, course materials, and theses, fulfilling the methodological proposal.

After a thorough reading of the material related to Medical Biomagnetism, combined with general knowledge of the Lymphatic System and considering the clinical practice of a significant number of biomagnetists who reported positive outcomes with the application of the Lymphatic Protocol, the suggested arrangement for its use is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Lymphatic Protocol (LP).

MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM PROTOCOL

Lymphatic

Protocol developed by Adrian. The magnet application convention follows that of the Instituto Par Magnético (IPM). Where red is seen (south pole), the north pole is against the skin, and where black is seen (north pole), the south pole is in contact with the skin. One south pole magnet applied over the Thymus, thirteen north pole magnets applied over lymph nodes. For the presentation of this protocol, the Biomagnetic Pair (BMP) from Medical Biomagnetism,

Chiasma/Chiasma (north pole applied to the right temporal region, south pole to the left temporal region) was added. Source: Bossa (2021); Calegari et al. (2023).

The LP (Lymphatic Protocol) developed by Adrian follows the convention of the Instituto Par Magnético (IPM). In this protocol, the BMP Chiasma/Chiasma is located near the temporal region and is the only BMP from Medical Biomagnetism present in the LP. A Biomagnetic Pair (BMP) is characterized by a bioelectromagnetic dysfunction at two points in the body where there is a presence of polarized charges. One point tends to have higher alkalinity than its physiological condition, in this case, the Right Chiasma, while the other tends to have higher acidity, the Left Chiasma. According to Durán (2008), this is a special BMP that, when impacted, tends to regulate the lymphatic system, assisting in the drainage process. The BMP Chiasma/Chiasma is used in cases of altered lymphatic flow, presence of limb lymphedema, leg pain, bruises, and tired eyes.

The other points in the LP are applied with north pole magnets (coloured on black, also referred to negative) (Calegari et al., 2023) according to their use in magnetotherapy on lymph nodes in the cervical, axillary, subclavian, brachial, inguinal, and popliteal (right and left) regions, as demonstrated in Figure 2. Additionally, one south pole magnet (red, also referred to positive) (Calegari et al., 2023) is applied directly over the thymus to stimulate it and over the kidneys to enhance fluid elimination.

The LP is an adaptation of Adrian's experience, supplemented with the BMP Chiasma/Chiasma. It is a tool of MB used for draining residual fluids resulting from metabolism and inflammatory processes, as well as being complementary in treatments for lymphatic flow blockage, promoting detoxification of the body (Durán, 2008; Bossa, 2021). It can be used by biomagnetists and other professionals, applied with other techniques, before or during Manual Lymphatic Drainage (MLD), with the purpose of enhancing its results.

For the application of the LP, the patient can be in a lying, sitting, or position compatible with other treatments. Medium-intensity magnets, between 1000 and 7500 Gauss, are placed simultaneously for a period of 30 to 40 minutes, and

the duration can be extended according to the organism's needs. The frequency of its use depends on the professional's recommendation or the organism's needs.

The LP is contraindicated for pregnant women in the first trimester of pregnancy and for individuals with battery-powered devices, as well as those who are hemodynamically unstable (Martínez, 2018). In magnetotherapy, it is essential to observe that the electrical energy of the north and south poles of the magnet, when applied to a living organism, produces different effects. Therefore, it is necessary to know the action of the energy of each pole on the locations exposed to Static Magnetic Fields (SMF) (Broeringmeyer, 1991; Foltran et al., 2023; Calegari et al., 2023; Drum et al., 2023; Ribeiro, 2016).

The north pole reduces the level of hydrogen and increases the level of oxygen, producing an alkaline metabolic response, contributing to the normalization of the pH and reducing protein activity (Broeringmeyer, 1991; Lima et al., 2023). As observed in the Perez study (2022), the application of both polarities resulted in increased fibroblast cell proliferation when exposed to SMF.

The south pole's energy can elevate the level of hydrogen ions and reduce the level of oxygen ions. Complementing the benefits of the north pole magnets proposed by the LP to enhance lymphatic drainage, when applied together, the south pole's energy increases activity and stimulates organ function, tonifying the thymus. It is directly associated with increased fluidity in vessel circulation, making organs and tissues more flexible, reducing stress and constrictions without weakening venous, arterial, and capillary walls, and assisting in red blood cell production (Broeringmeyer, 1991).

Therapies with SMF are used to treat various conditions such as arthritis, chronic pain, wound healing, insomnia, headaches, and others. They have a normalizing action on vascular tone that can have beneficial impacts in situations where tissue perfusion is needed, producing homeostatic effects (Colbert, 2009; Wyszowska, 2018).

The use of the LP can be indicated for reducing localized or generalized edema caused by inflammatory processes, continuous medication use, chemotherapy, and other factors. It can also be complementary to treatments for renal, cardiac, vascular disorders, venous thrombosis, and embolisms. In addition to improving circulation and consequent oxygenation of the body, stimulating the immune system to perform its functions, helping to balance gland metabolism, promoting weight loss processes, and assisting in post-surgical drainage. A study with rodents using magnetic therapy demonstrated a significant increase in plasma levels and an elevation in blood parameters, such as white blood cells, lymphocytes, hemoglobin, and hematocrit, after a single 24-hour exposure to SMF (Wyszkowska, 2018).

CONCLUSION

In this study, the Lymphatic Protocol (LP), a tool of the Medical Biomagnetism (MB) technique, was presented, which has therapeutic potential to be applied as an adjuvant treatment for generalized or localized edema and other symptoms related to lymphatic system disorders.

Considering that the application of Medical Biomagnetism Protocols is non-invasive and easy to apply, requiring little training and can be self-applied, it is concluded that this is a safe protocol to be used. However, further studies using the Lymphatic Protocol are necessary to determine the required duration of magnet application and to validate the results provided by the protocol.

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¹Student of the Graduate Program in Biomagnetism and Bioenergetics Applied to Health, Faculty of Technology – FATEC, Curitiba – Paraná – Brazil.

²Co-supervisor of the Graduate Program in Biomagnetism and Bioenergetics Applied to Health, Faculty of Technology – FATEC, Curitiba – Paraná – Brazil.

³Supervisor of the Graduate Program in Biomagnetism and Bioenergetics Applied to Health, Faculty of Technology – FATEC, Curitiba – Paraná – Brazil.

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